

Some Recent Developments in High Polymers*

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Phenomenal development has been taking place in the field of high polymers, and I shall report today some recent progress in the field. I had the privilege to listen to the two opening lectures by Prof. H. Mark in the two latest international symposia on high polymers, one in Prague in August 1965 and another lately in Tokyo (October, 1966) and I shall draw copiously from what I heard in these two lectures with particular regard to thermostable polymers. Today's lecture would touch on the following topics.

- (1) Plastics in the Sixties
- (2) High temperature resistant polymers
- (3) Synthetic Enzyme analogues.

1. *Plastics in the Sixties.*

The emphasis in the plastics development in recent years has been on engineering plastics—plastics which are tough, hard and rigid, which have combination of properties of metal, wood, glass & ceramic and leather, and which can replace metals as materials of construction. Some technologically important high polymers developed during the sixties are—

- (1) Acetal resins
- (2) Polycarbonates
- (3) ABS resins
- (4) Phenoxy resins
- (5) Chlorinated polyethers
- (6) Polyallomers
- (7) Polyimides
- (8) Corfam (Synthetic leather)

Acetal resins or polyformaldehyde was introduced in 1960 by Dupont under the trade name Delrin. The terminal hydroxyl group of the polymeric chain is capped by a suitable chemical reaction for chemical stability. Another variety is a copolymer of formaldehyde and trioxane (triformaldehyde) which has unusual chemical interest in the fact that the copolymer units tie knots randomly along the chain and these knots resist 'unzipping' of the chain. Due to its high strength and stiffness it is used as industrial parts, appliance parts, automotive parts and in over 7000 different engineering applications.

introduced at about the same time as the acetals is one of the better examples of

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engineering thermoplastics. It is almost transparent, easy to process and has excellent toughness, impact strength and rigidity. It has received widespread use in many applications where previously metals or glass were used.

ABS resins derived from acrylonitrile-butadiene-styrene and introduced in 1962, fulfil very closely the ideal of a tough hard and rigid thermoplastic. It also combines a good balance of other properties such as dimensional stability, chemical resistance, etc. Styrene appears to impart good fabrication properties, acrylonitrile imparts the chemical resistance, surface hardness and tensile and flexural strength, and butadiene imparts good ductility and toughness. Because of this balance of properties it is used in almost all areas of industry from appliances and automobile parts to toys and luggages. In price it is also competitive with many engineering materials per unit volume basis.

The development of this resin is of great physicochemical interest as it affords an example of development of desirable physical properties by proper physical and chemical blending. Copolymers of the three monomers did not have the desirable combination of properties. Neither a dispersion of polybutadiene in styrene-acrylonitrile copolymer for toughening achieved quite the desirable end. To make the former more compatible with the latter, polybutadiene was grafted with suitable proportions of styrene and acrylonitrile and this composite polymer dispersed in a matrix of styrene-acrylonitrile copolymer is the present-day ABS resins of versatile engineering use.

The chlorinated polyether, $\left[-O-CH_2-\overset{\overset{CH_2Cl}{|}}{C}-CH_2 \right]_n$ is a polymer of chlorinated

oxetane obtained from pentaerythritol. It has a chlorine content of 46% of the weight of the polymer which imparts to it exceptional corrosion resistance. With other desirable properties it is very suitable for production of equipment for chemical and processing systems and is thus extensively used.

The phenoxy resins (introduced in 1962 by Union Carbide) are basically the well-known epoxy resins (the 'miracle' adhesive) but of at least ten times higher molecular weight. Its unique property is high dimensional stability combined with lowest permeability to oxygen and many other gases. It is widely used in the production of precision injection-molded electronic parts for computer and other critical instruments as also in high-fidelity sound records.

The name 'Polyallomers' has been coined to designate a crystalline thermoplastic polymer produced from two or more different monomers. This is neither a blend or mixture of two homopolymers nor a copolymer of the component monomers; it can be roughly described as a kind of ordered copolymer. For example, the tenite polyallomer (1962) obtained from ethylene and propylene, is at least as good as, if not better, than the crystalline polypropylene of commerce but is much cheaper due to its ethylene content. This is called a hinging plastic and finds wide application in injection-molded carrying cases with integral hinges.

The polyimides (1965, polymer S P, H. film by Du Pont) are characterised by high thermal stability of at least up to 750°F. They have good electrical properties and

excellent frictional properties. Though yet of somewhat high price it is of wide industrial and military applications where its superior properties are of advantage.

The synthetic leather viz. corfam of Du Pont has already made considerable inroad into the field of shoe-uppers. It scores over all other leather-like polymers in being of a micro-porous structure of high water-vapour permeability as in leather. The polymer used is polyurethan made microporous by a special process.

2. *Polymers of High Thermal Stability and Mechanical Strength*

The usual attack on the problem of imparting higher mechanical strength and thermal stability has been through cross-linking or crystallization. Crystalline polypropylene paved the way but it was soon realised that though crystallinity in a chain improves the property tremendously as compared to the same chain polymer in the randomly-oriented non-crystalline state the melting point limit cannot be pushed by this change much far beyond 300°C or so. Cross-linking does not help much as the polymer becomes insoluble and difficult to process. A new principle has been lately pressed into service in attempts to prepare polymers of hitherto inaccessible properties or combination of properties. The new principle is to produce a polymer chain which is itself rigid in structure. In a sense this rigid chemical structure is more or less a structure known as 'ladder' structure. The goal is to produce polymers in the melting range of 600°–800°C, Young's modulus in the region of 500,000 pounds per square inch, high toughness and comparatively high elongation at break. Some recent attempts are as follows.

The first class of the rigid chain polymers belongs to chains of ring compounds making the big molecule quite rigid. Poly-p-phenylene (i) is a typical example of such a polymer

and numerous others have been prepared. All these materials so far prepared are not highly crystalline and melt round 700-800°C.

The drawback for these polymers is their low solubility which has been overcome by applying substituent to the ring and thereby improving their solubility even at high molecular weights. Examples of such polymers are:

Another type of rigid chain polymers is made by copolymerization, an example being oxidative coupling of biphenyl with benzene and various other polymers. Some examples are shown below:

Another class of compound constitutes of linear chains of aromatic rings made more flexible by the introduction of various groups like-O-, -CH₂-, -S-, etc. as 'spacers'.

Such substances are more processable but of somewhat lower-melting point (softening range 500-600°C). The following are typical examples.

Also cross-linking can be introduced by substitution of $\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}$ gps. eg.

Precursor Method—The next class of the rigid chain polymers are polycondensation products (precursors) where a certain percentage of the bonds is left open and unconjugated. During final cure after casting additional cyclization takes place through these openings. The number of such bonds to be left open depends on the processibility of the Precursor polymer. To estimate the degree of unconjugated bonds one studies the absorption spectra.

The last class of these thermostable polymers are the highly condensed polymers, an example being highly condensed polyacrylonitrile ("Pluton") as shown below. Another example is the condensation product (see ii below) Terephthoyl cyanate (terephthonyl cyanate oxide). These are highly heat resistant and do not burn or melt even when held on red hot heater or a lighted burner.

The commercial application or handling of all these polymers has been made possible by a method named emulsion or suspension spinning developed by Julian Phil. In this method cellulose xanthate is used as a carrier and any polymer, e.g. teflon, silica, even carbon can be spun into fibres and the cellulose xanthate got rid off afterwards.

3. *Synthetic Polymers as Enzyme analogues*

I would like to mention very briefly some recent work of tremendous future possibility. I purposely make this very brief mention to draw attention of my young colleagues in India that here lies a field where there is a potentiality of producing results of the highest rank of great theoretical and experimental significance even with the very limited experimental facilities at our disposal in India. Any chemist prepared to put in relentless hard work can easily persecute this challenging line of research in the poorly equipped laboratories obtaining in our country. The work in question is to synthesize polymers and to look for its catalytic power similar to enzymes. Overberger's recent work is an example to the point. He has synthesised polyvinyl imidazole as also poly 5 or 6 vinyl benzimidazole and some copolymers, and using *p*-nitrophenyl acetate as substrate has demonstrated these polymers (and not the dimers or so) to have good catalytic power for hydrolysis at suitable *pH*. This conclusively shows that the specific polyfunctionality necessary for enzyme-like activity can be synthetically produced and it may be confidently predicted that the day may not be far off when man-made enzymes could be available to perform highly specific chemical jobs.

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